

Final query used in Step 2 of data collection

```
SELECT
Comments.id,
Comments.Post_id,
Comments.Score,
Comments.Text,
Comments.Creation_date,

Posts.Id,
Posts.Post_Type_Id,
Posts.Parent_Id,
Posts.Score,
Posts.Tags,
Posts.Comment_Count

FROM
    bigquery-public-data.stackoverflow.comments AS Comments
INNER JOIN
    bigquery-public-data.stackoverflow.stackoverflow_posts AS Posts
ON
    Comments.post_id=Posts.Id

WHERE
Comments.Text LIKE '%humanist%'
OR Comments.Text LIKE '%human-cent%'
OR Comments.Text LIKE '%human nature%'
OR Comments.Text LIKE '%user-focused%'
OR Comments.Text LIKE '%user-friendly%'

OR Comments.Text LIKE '%end[ -]user%'
OR Comments.Text LIKE '%user experience%'
OR Comments.Text LIKE '%ethical%'
OR Comments.Text LIKE '%ethics%'
OR Comments.Text LIKE '%ethical%'

OR Comments.Text LIKE '%core beliefs%'
OR Comments.Text LIKE '%against [a-z][a-z][a-z] beliefs%'
OR Comments.Text LIKE '%against my beliefs%'
```

```
OR Comments.Text LIKE '%against [a-z][a-z][a-z][a-z] beliefs%'
OR Comments.Text LIKE '%against [a-z][a-z][a-z] values%'
OR Comments.Text LIKE '%against my beliefs%'
OR Comments.Text LIKE '%against [a-z][a-z][a-z][a-z] values%'
OR Comments.Text LIKE '%human value%'
OR Comments.Text LIKE '%moral [^o][^f]%'
OR Comments.Text LIKE '%society%'
OR Comments.Text LIKE '%social[^.].%'
```

```
ORDER BY RAND()
```